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Phase 3

Report on the containerisation of EC-Earth 4

Deliverable D1.5

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Lead author(s): Uwe Fladrich (SMHI)

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Contact details

Project Office: esiwace3@bsc.es

Website: www.esiwace.eu

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/esiwace>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@esiwace880>

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1. Abstract/publishable summary

Containerisation is a virtualisation technology that allows to abstract the dependencies of complex software packages, such as Earth system models, and makes it much easier to port software to new machines and provide a reproducible installation environment. The objective of this deliverable is to design, develop, and test a containerised version of EC-Earth4, thus allowing a proto-type deployment of a simple climate model simulation workflow in a testing environment.

Based on a review of current containerisation technology, the Apptainer software has been selected for the containerisation of EC-Earth4 because it is well adapted to HPC systems, easy to use and well documented and supported. The container design process addresses important technical aspects, such as the scope of containerisation, selection of the base operating system and other components, details of the container build system, performance considerations for HPC systems, and the workflow adaptation for experiments with the containerised model. The proposed container design answers and documents most of these issues, providing a prototype solution for EC-Earth4 as well as a general approach and recommendations for other Earth system models.

The finalised container is tested in a coupled atmosphere-ocean-sea-ice configuration with production output, running ten-year experiments with automatic restarts on the test system. Performance issues are discussed with regard to the target EuroHPC pre-exascale systems. A detailed example for deployment of the containerised version is documented.

2. Conclusion and results

The development of the containerised EC-Earth4 version has shown, or confirmed, that containerisation of a large software package is a technically complex task. While the containerisation of simple programs and services has become state-of-the-art and is well documented, Earth system models do not fall into that category. They are built from multiple components that usually come with a complex list of dependencies, and are often parallelised hybridly, using MPI and OpenMP. This requires a container design that controls a complex software stack spanning across both the container and the host system software and hardware drivers.

Secondly, the workflow of Earth system model experiments usually covers a number of extra tools at build and runtime. In the containerisation of (web) services, this problem is usually solved by implementing micro services, each running within a separate container. However, this approach requires container orchestration, which is difficult to adapt to the HPC infrastructure used for Earth system models. Hence, the EC-Earth4 container is monolithic, including all the software needed for the build and runtime environment to support a full model experiment workflow. However, this implies (again) a more complex container design.

Despite the complexity, the proposed container design is quite general and can apply to other Earth system models. The container build process is rather generic and modular, which will ease the application to other models. The containerisation approach is documented and the build scripts are available on the EC-Earth Gitlab and ready for further dissemination within the ESiWACE3 project and the community. The computational performance of the containerised model is reasonable, but not

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necessarily satisfactory for this prototype. Issues and possible solutions to performance issues are discussed in this document.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to achieving the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Grant Agreement:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable
A1: Transfer and establish knowledge and technology for efficient and scalable simulations of weather and climate across the Earth system modelling community in Europe.	Yes
A2: Close common technology gaps in the knowledge and toolbox for high-resolution Earth system modelling via joint developments across the European community.	Yes
A3: Serve as a sustainable community hub for training, communication, and dissemination for high-performance computing for weather and climate modelling in Europe.	Yes

Specific goals in the work plan	Contribution of this deliverable
01: Increase efficiency of weather and climate simulations on state-of-the-art supercomputers.	Yes
02: Design tools to close technology gaps for high performance computing.	Yes
03: Develop tools to tackle the data challenge of high-resolution weather and climate modelling.	No
04: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via targeted services.	Yes
05: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via training and capacity building.	Yes
06: Build a well-connected and inclusive community for high-resolution Earth system modelling across Earth system science and HPC and establish connections and knowledge transfer between existing European initiatives.	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

Objectives and scope

The main objective of this deliverable is to “design, develop, and deploy a containerised version of EC-Earth4 and a simple model experiment workflow, building on established container technologies and standards”, as specified in task 1.4 of WP1. This objective is broken down into the following specific tasks:

1. Review available containerisation technology, in particular such that can be effectively used for Earth system models and on scientific HPC platforms;
2. design a containerisation approach for the EC-Earth 4 model, focusing on a GCM configuration, a single-experiment use case and an appropriate (i.e. EuroHPC pre-exascale-like) HPC platform;
3. document the chosen approach and any technical issues, including aspects of further use for other models and different platforms.

Hence, the focus of this deliverable is on (i) a workable prototype and (ii) a well documented approach and procedure for the containerisation of EC-Earth 4.

The EC-Earth 4 model

Short description

EC-Earth4 is a post-CMIP6 generation Earth System Model developed and used by the EC-Earth consortium¹. The model is under continuous development in preparation for CMIP7, but a first release (EC-Earth4.0.0) has been published in June 2024 and this release is used here for the purpose of containerisation. This model version supports GCM configurations (coupled atmosphere-ocean-sea-ice) in different resolutions (ranging from coarse to high-resolution). The main model components are OpenIFS43r3 [1] for the atmosphere, NEMO4.2.2 [2] for the ocean, SI3 [3] for sea-ice, OASIS3-MCT 5.2 [4] for coupling, and XIOS2.5 [5] for writing output from atmosphere, ocean and sea-ice. The source code of the components is mostly identical to the upstream versions by their respective development teams, however, some developments are included to support specific EC-Earth features.

Technical structure and dependencies

Technically, the EC-Earth4 model consists of the actual model code (i.e. the source code of all model components), and the build and runtime environment scripts. All components add to the overall rather complex list of dependencies of the model. Compiling the source code of the components produces a multi-executable, hybrid MPI+OpenMP application, for which the runtime environment is particularly adapted. The list of EC-Earth4 dependencies includes:

- Fortran and C++ compilers
- MPI and OpenMP
- (parallel) NetCDF, ecCodes and other third-party libraries

¹ <https://www.ec-earth.org>

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- Python and conda environments
- Build and runtime tools: ScriptEngine and rdy2cpl

It is noteworthy that the build and runtime tools come with their own list of (nontrivial) dependencies, mostly from the Python universe. This has an implication for the scope of containerisation (i.e. what will be packed inside the container), as will be discussed later. Although the build and runtime tools are specific to EC-Earth4, the situation is similar for other Earth system models, which usually depend on their own set of tools.

HPC containers

Overview

In computing, containers implement operating-system-level virtualisation, mostly with the goal of better portability and reproducibility. The main idea is to provide most of the application dependencies with the container, thus making the process of porting to a new system much easier and avoiding differences induced by dependencies (e.g. in library versions). Containerisation differs from other virtualisation techniques, like virtual machines or virtual environments, by placing the interface between container and host system at the Linux kernel level (non-Linux systems are not considered here). This means that the container includes its own filesystem (with libraries and configuration files), while using the host systems Linux kernel to execute system calls.

Different software packages for container virtualisation are available, including:

- Docker [6]
- Apptainer/Singularity [7,8]
- Podman [9]
- Sarus [10]

Important aspects for choosing any particular software in the context of this deliverable include: the applicability for scientific software; support for HPC systems, including high-performance interconnects; software licensing and documentation, particularly for scientific software development projects.

Of the available options, Apptainer/Singularity is chosen for the implementation of the EC-Earth4 container, because it

- is developed with focus to *“run complex applications on HPC clusters in a simple, portable, and reproducible way”* [11]
- is open source,
- is popular and well supported at many academic and HPC sites, including national and EuroHPC systems (LUMI, Leonardo, MareNostrum5),
- allows non-privileged users to build and run containers,
- has native support for high-performance interconnects, such as InfiniBand and Intel Omni-Path,
- integrates with common resource managers, particularly SLURM,
- supports Docker imports, allowing to build containers on top of Docker Hub images.

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As an alternative, the use of Docker for the containerisation of EC-Earth4 has been considered because it is hugely popular for virtualisation of applications and services. However, Docker is not as well adapted to HPC systems and scientific software development. One major issue is the client-server architecture, which relies on a Docker daemon that usually runs with superuser privileges on the host system. This implies security issues that lead most HPC centres to disallow running Docker containers on their HPC systems. Even though the other containerisation platforms (Podman, Saurus) have a daemon-less architecture and are well adapted to the HPC use case, they do not possess the same level of popularity and support as Singularity/Apptainer, when it comes to development, documentation, and availability on HPC systems.

Apptainer/Singularity

Apptainer/Singularity is a container platform that has become popular on HPC systems due to its ease of use, security model, support for HPC hardware, bootstrapping from Docker images, and an active user and development community. It is available on the EuroHPC pre-exascale tier-0 supercomputers LUMI (LUMI consortium, CSC), Leonardo (CINECA), MareNostrum5 (BSC) and can be considered as widely supported on most machines that are used to run Earth system models. It is available on most machines at the National Supercomputing Center (NSC) in Sweden, where the EC-Earth4 container was developed and tested.

The software started out as the Singularity open-source project in 2015, but has been renamed Apptainer after a fork (which retained the name Singularity) in 2020. For most practical matters (and as far as this deliverable is concerned), Apptainer and Singularity are drop-in compatible. All development and testing has been done with Apptainer version 1.3.3.

Starting from a plain text definition file, Apptainer builds containers in the Singularity Image File (SIF) format [11]. The definition file specifies the base container (bootstrapping), tasks for software installation, environment setup, and files to copy into the container. The resulting container file is an executable that can be run directly on the host system, or by using a specific Apptainer run command. Directories can be mounted into the container at runtime, allowing the containerised application to access host file systems and read or write files.

Docker images can be used (among other options) as base containers for Apptainer. Thus, one can make use of the huge variety of base operating system containers at the Docker hub, which includes images well adapted for HPC applications.

Apptainer also allows base containers to be local files, which includes Apptainer containers. Thus, containers can be built “on top” of each other, resulting in a “stacked” container design, where the final container is built from layers of previously built ones.

MPI container

While building and running simple containers with Apptainer is relatively simple, including MPI programs is not, mainly because of two technical aspects:

- process management at MPI startup, particularly across multi-node supercomputers

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- handling of inter-connection hardware for MPI communication

Both aspects conflict inherently with some of the assumptions made for *simple* containers, as will be discussed soon. Hence, performant MPI containers for HPC systems need a more careful, and more complex, design and configuration.

MPI process management

At the startup of an MPI application on a cluster computer, the MPI launcher needs to contact daemons on each node in order to have them start the correct executable and number of processes. Possibly, the launcher also has to start the daemons on remote nodes, but this is not usually the case on HPC systems. After the processes have been started, they will connect back to the daemon (usually during `MPI_Init`) to exchange connection information with all the other processes in the MPI universe.

A protocol for starting MPI processes has been established, called the Process Management Interface (PMI, [12]). There are different PMI versions (PMI1, PMI2, PMIx), which have been implemented in various frameworks.

The difficulty with containers is that the MPI launcher *within a container* cannot easily start an MPI task on another node because that new process will refer to the host system, not the container. Hence, the executable (and MPI libraries) will not exist on the host system on the other node. For example, if we used the `mpirun` launcher within a container (`foo.sif`) to start executable (`/opt/bin/foo` in the container):

```
host> aptainer run foo.sif
container> mpirun -np 4 /opt/bin/foo
```

then `mpirun` in an multi-node setup would contact an MPI daemon on the “other” node and request to start `/opt/bin/foo` on that node. This will not work because the executable does not exist on the host system (and neither will any library that `foo` is linked against in the container). An exception to this rule is if all MPI processes are started on the same node, in which case the (child-)processes are started within the container and things work out fine. However, this would limit the MPI application to one node and therefore few processes.

Another option is to start the application by telling the MPI launcher to start the container itself. This is supported by some MPI launchers, such as the SLURM [13] `srun` command:

```
host> srun -n 4 aptainer run /opt/bin/foo.sif
```

This will start the container on the “other” node and run the `foo.sif` container executable and allow the MPI initialisation across nodes. A prerequisite is, however, that the host system’s SLURM installation and the containerised `foo` application use the same PMI version. The SLURM `srun` command provides `--mpi` flag to specify which PMI variant should be used (from the list of supported versions). The MPI inside the container needs to support at least one matching version, which somewhat limits the portability of the container.

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The latter approach is often recommended by HPC centres when dealing with containerised MPI applications. However, it requires that the application is started *from outside the container*, which means that the model runtime environment (i.e. start scripts etc.) cannot easily be included in the container. This is further discussed below.

MPI communication hardware

MPI subroutines like `MPI_Send` and `MPI_Receive` call the MPI library, which in turn calls some lower level system libraries. At some point in the call stack, system calls are executed, marking the interface to the Linux kernel. Subsequently, the kernel calls a device driver, which instructs the underlying hardware to send/receive the data. The distinction between libraries and the kernel is important because the former are included in the container while the latter is run on the host system. This means for MPI communication that the libraries in the container can only use features available in the host system kernel and driver modules. Initially, this is not a big problem because MPI implementations provide communication via simple channels (e.g. tcp) that are part of every Linux system. However, this is not very efficient on HPC systems, which usually include special interconnection hardware (e.g. InfiniBand [14] or Intel Omni-Path [15]) for inter-node communication and advanced modules for shared-memory communication within a node. In order to make use of these high-performance communication channels, the container MPI must include the interfaces for the particular hardware, which may limit the portability of the container.

Implementation

Container scope and general architecture

Deciding on the scope of the EC-Earth4 container is a first, and important, design decision: which components of the model should be included in the container and which should run on the host system? A minimal containerisation would just include the multi-executable MPI application (i.e. OpenIFS, NEMO, OASIS, XIOS for EC-Earth) in the container and leave the runtime environment outside. However, this would imply that the runtime environment, including all of its dependencies, still needs to be installed (manually) on the target system and that would defeat the purpose of the containerisation to a certain degree. Hence, it is decided to include the complete build and runtime environment in the container. Even though this makes the container configuration and build considerably more complex, it retains much more of the portability and makes running the containerised model much easier.

The EC-Earth4 runtime environment is based on ScriptEngine [16], a Python software package that executes scripts written in YAML. The same tool is also used for the build environment, where scripts are provided to compile and link all components. ScriptEngine is easiest installed in a conda [17] environment, so the container needs to provide the conda package manager and a default virtual conda environment that provides the required Python packages with their dependencies.

Another consequence of containerising the runtime environment is that batch jobs have to be submitted from within the container. This is not trivial, as mentioned earlier, and most MPI container guides either do not cover this step or even advise against it. Nevertheless, job submission is an integral part of the EC-Earth4 experiment workflow (for long experiments, for example), so it is needed for a workable

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containerisation. Submitting jobs from within the container can be achieved by installing a compatible batch system (here: SLURM [13]) inside the container and making sure that it can connect to the host system and submit jobs.

There exist other schedulers, like PBS or LSF. However, only SLURM is considered here for the following reasons: In contrast to PBS or LSF, SLURM is open source. This is crucial, because the scheduler needs to be built inside the container in order to choose the correct PMI version and modules. Moreover, the container architecture depends on the availability of technical information about some of the inner workings of the scheduler, which is not easily obtained for proprietary software. Last not least, EC-Earth4 is itself dependent on SLURM for submitting jobs. Porting to other schedulers has been attempted, but not succeeded. Overall, the adaption of the container approach to other schedulers is probably feasible, but beyond the scope of this deliverable.

In order to make sure that the containerised SLURM, the host SLURM and the MPI application can interoperate during job submission and the MPI startup phase, they need to use the same PMI (Process Management Interface, see above) protocol and version. Hence, a full installation of PMIx [18] (which is supported by the host SLURM) is included and used to build SLURM as well as MPI inside the container.

OpenMPI [19] is chosen as the MPI implementation inside the container. Besides being compatible with PMIx, it also comes with the Modular Component Architecture (MCA, [20]), which is a system that allows selecting hardware drivers at runtime. This enables the container to efficiently use interconnection hardware on different platforms, as long as appropriate drivers have been included at build time.

The EC-Earth4 model writes parallel output in the NetCDF4 format and depends on the NetCDF and HDF5 libraries for that purpose. Both libraries, in turn, need to be built against the MPI used in the container. Hence, HDF5 and NetCDF are compiled during the container build process.

The GNU Compiler Collection (GCC, including gcc, g++, gfortran compilers, [21]) is used to compile all dependencies and the EC-Earth4 components. Besides being widely available and supported, GCC is also highly compatible with the main system libraries on Linux systems. The GCC backend provides a wide range of optimisation techniques for modern processor architectures, so efficiency on most HPC systems can be expected.

All software components used in the container built are open source, well documented, and supported, which makes them readily available for the development and relatively easy to work with. Therefore, the final container build does not depend on proprietary licences (except for the OpenIFS licence for the actual EC-Earth source code, which can be easily obtained for research institutes).

It has been mentioned before that Apptainer allows for stacked containers (i.e. building containers on top of other containers) and this feature is extensively used. Compiling software like SLURM or OpenMPI takes a lot of time, so it should be avoided to compile all software for every container build. Moreover, this approach also modularises the container design and easily allows to exchange, for example, one component for another (e.g. different versions of OpenMPI). The build process of the containers is automatised with GNU make, which simplifies and speeds up the creation of new container versions.

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The complete container stack, in build order, is:

1. base OS + development tools
2. PMIx
3. SLURM
4. OpenMPI
5. HDF5
6. NetCDF
7. Conda + Python dependencies
8. EC-Earth4 components

The complete system of the containerised EC-Earth4 executables, dependencies, and runtime system is given the name ECEC, for EC-Earth Container. ECEC also includes an example setup and starting scripts for the containerised model, thus providing the base for a complete ESM experiment workflow.

ECEC: Container build

This section provides further technical details for the individual containers that make up the ECEC stack. The specs for each container are defined in an associated definition file for Apptainer and the build for each container is triggered by GNUmake, using a makefile that defines the dependencies between the containers and definition (and auxiliary) files. The container definitions will use parallel build whenever possible, employing all available cores in the environment.

Base OS

The base container provides the underlying operating system (OS) as well as most of the dependencies that can be installed as binary packages via the OS package manager. AlmaLinux9 [22] is used as base OS for the EC-Earth4 container, an open source Linux distribution focused on long-term stability and production-grade robustness. AlmaLinux is binary compatible with RedHat Enterprise Linux [23], a distribution that is widely used for HPC systems. A prerequisite for building host-compatible containers is to make sure that the libraries included in the container match the kernel version run on the host. By using version 9 of AlmaLinux it is made sure that libraries and kernel versions are compatible for most recent HPC systems.

The base container pulls the `almalinux:9` Docker image from Docker Hub and uses the OS as the starting point. Along with the base OS, a number of binary dependencies are installed:

- GNU Compilers (gcc, g++, gfortran), Perl
- Development tools (GNU make, autoconf, automake, ...)
- Hardware related libraries needed for PMIx/SLURM/OpenMPI: libevent (event-driven callback functions), hwloc (portable hardware locality), ...
- MUNGE library (process authentication service for creating and validating credentials in HPC cluster environments, [24]), needed for SLURM
- EC-Earth dependencies: ecCodes [25], OpenBLAS

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These dependencies do not need compiling and can therefore be installed as binary packages with the OS package manager.

PMIx

OpenPMIx [26] version 4.2.9 (at the time of writing) is downloaded from Github at container build time and configured and compiled with autoconf and GNU make in the container. This version of OpenPMIx provides the `pmix_v4` plugin for SLURM, which is exactly the same as used by the host SLURM installation. This version match is important for interoperability. Tests have been made with the PMIx package provided by the AlmaLinux9 OS (i.e. without compiling OpenPMIx from source), but this version provides `pmix_v3`, which is incompatible with the host system. The exact PMI versions supported by the host system can be checked by running, for example, the `srun --mpi=list` command.

SLURM

In order to have the container SLURM interact correctly with the host SLURM, the following points have to be considered:

- matching SLURM versions
- matching SLURM PMIx plugin versions
- other SLURM plugins
- matching SLURM user and group IDs
- host configuration and data needed at runtime

The SLURM version in the container is picked such that it has the same major and minor version numbers as on the host. On the test system, SLURM 22.05.8 is installed, so 22.05.9 is used in the container (the latest 22.05 version). During configuration, the `--with-pmix` option is passed to make sure that SLURM is compiled using the container OpenMPIx version compiled before.

SLURM provides a plugin mechanism called SPANK (Slurm Plug-in Architecture for Node and job (K)ontrol) and the test system uses a SPANK plugin named `private-tmp` [27]. This plugin is needed in the container as well, so it is downloaded and compiled at container build time.

A security mechanism is in place that requires the SLURM installation inside the container to run under the same user and group ID as the SLURM instance on the host. Hence, it is made sure during the container build that the `slurm` user exists and has the same IDs. The container build script provides the `SLURM_UID` and `SLURM_GID` variables to allow adoption to the host system settings.

Once the SLURM container is built, it should be possible to submit jobs from within the container to the host batch system. For that to work, the SLURM configuration (`/etc/slurm`) and the MUNGE runtime data (`/run/munge`) need to be bind-mounted in the container.

OpenMPI

The test system comes with OpenMPI [19] version 4.1.4 installed, so for compatibility reasons (although not strictly necessary), OpenMPI 4.1.6 is compiled in the container. Keeping the major/minor versions of

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host/container MPIs in sync will help to ensure that the PMIx version can handle the startup of MPI applications.

During the configuration of OpenMPI in the container, it is made sure that PMIx (`--with-pmix`) and SLURM (`--with-slurm`) are included in the compilation. The older PMI protocol is disabled (`--without-pmi`) to make sure that PMIx is used.

At this stage, support for interconnection hardware for the target systems should be included in the OpenMPI build. Many of the drivers possibly needed are included by default in the configuration and the actual configuration of the driver subroutines can therefore be done at runtime. In cases where included drivers cause compatibility problems, they can be excluded from the build (in case they cannot be switched off during runtime).

HDF5

A recent version of HDF5 (version 1.12.2) is compiled in the container, including support for parallel file I/O (`--with-parallel`). This will use the previously installed MPI implementation.

NetCDF

Based on the previous HDF5 installation, NetCDF is compiled, which includes NetCDF4 support for parallel files via HDF5. Support for NetCDF C, C++, and Fortran APIs is provided as separate software packages, so each language support has to be downloaded and compiled individually.

Conda + Python dependencies

The conda package and virtual environment manager is installed in the container using Miniforge. The conda-forge channel is configured as default to make sure the conda packages are found on, and downloaded from, that channel. The Miniforge installer is downloaded from Github in the container build script and conda is installed under `/opt/conda` in the container. Only one virtual conda environment (the base environment) is used in the container, all packages are installed and the environment is activated per default. Beside the conda package manager (and inside the conda base environment), the `pip` package manager is installed for packages provided at PyPI (the Python Package Index, [28]).

Using conda and pip, the Python dependencies are installed: ScriptEngine (`scriptengine`), including extra task packages (`scriptengine-tasks-hpc`) and Ready2couple (`rdy2cp1`, [29]). It is worth noting that the installation of `rdy2cp1` triggers the installation of MPI for Python (`mpi4py`, [30]) and under-the-hood compilation of MPI code that will use the previously installed OpenMPI compiler wrapper and libraries.

EC-Earth4 components

Finally, the actual EC-Earth4 source code is downloaded, compiled, and installed in the container. The source code is cloned from the Gitlab repository hosted by the EC-Earth consortium. A valid user account is needed for this step due to the licence that covers OpenIFS, which forbids unrestricted distribution of the code.

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EC-Earth4 uses ScriptEngine for the build step and one of the YAML configuration files describe the platform settings for compilation (compiler and library settings, among other things). The containerised version comes with a platform file that specifies the settings for the container, so no further adoption to the target setting (i.e. porting) is needed.

Once all EC-Earth components are compiled, this completes the container build. A clean-up step is included in the build scripts, which will remove all object files, etc. and only leave libraries and executables. The final container file has a size of around 800 MB on the test system.

ECEC: runtime scripting

Building a container that includes the model executables, dependencies and runtime tools is not enough to allow users to run numerical experiments with EC-Earth4. The workflow of model experiments is more complex and includes, at least, setting up experiment configuration files and providing input data. This is an important difference compared to simpler containerised applications that can run on the command line by executing the container with some flags or options.

As mentioned before, EC-Earth4 uses ScriptEngine for runtime configuration and the execution of runscrips written in YAML. The same approach is applied for the containerised version, minimising the effort to switch between containerised and non-containerised versions of the model. The main difference (and simplification) is that all scripts that deal with platform specific configurations are provided within the container and, thus, hidden from the user.

A simple top-level run script (`ecec`) is provided, which allows users to provide an experiment configuration (a ScriptEngine YAML script, as used for non-containerised EC-Earth4) and specify input and output directories for initial and output data, respectively. Furthermore, the container runtime needs two environment variables be set:

```
ECEC_BINDIR=<absolute path to container wrapper script dir>  
ECEC_CONTAINER=<absolute path to ecec.sif container file>
```

where the container wrapper scripts are provided with the EC-Earth4 sources (see not below) and `ecec.sif` is the Apptainer container file previously built. Note that it is important to use absolute paths, relative paths will not work! As a final configuration step, `ECEC_BINDIR` needs to be included in the user's search `PATH`.

After the variables are set and the user experiment configuration is adapted (length of the run, initial conditions, etc.), an experiment with the containerised EC-Earth4 version can be started on the command line like:

```
> ecec -i <initial data dir> -o <run dir> <user experiment config>.yaml
```

The `ecec` runscrip will take care of mounting the necessary directories (initial data and run directories, SLURM directories), start the container and run ScriptEngine with the correct scripts (the user's experiment configuration and the container platform files).

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Technical note on wrappers

The container runtime includes two wrappers for scripts that are submitted by the runtime environment from within the container: `se` (for ScriptEngine) and `r2c` (for Ready2couple). The reason those wrappers are needed is that the scripts have to be found both on the host system and within the container. *Within* the container, they should execute in the usual way, but *outside* the container (i.e. on the host system), they should start the container file and execute “themselves” *within* the container. This is exactly what the wrappers are doing, checking whether they are started inside or outside the container and starting the “right” script or the container.

A further detail in this context is that the wrappers must exist identically both within and outside the container (even though in different paths). The reason is that SLURM actually copies scripts at submit time. Thus, when a script is submitted from within the container, it is copied into a SLURM directory. Later, when it is time to run the job, the copied(!) script is executed on the host system.

Recipe for running the containerised EC-Earth 4

The following recipe summarises the usage of the containerised EC-Earth4 model:

```
# get EC-Earth sources; a valid account is needed!
> git clone <ece-4-repository-url> ece-4-container
> cd ece-4-container
> git checkout dev/apptainer # code kept in separate branch
> cd scripts/apptainer

# alternative 1: build the container
> make

# alternative 2: get a pre-built container file from elsewhere
> cp <path-to-container>/ecec.sif ./

# set ECEC environment
> export ECEC_BINDIR=$(readlink -f bin) # readlink -f converts
                                       # to absolute path
> export PATH=$ECEC_BINDIR:$PATH
> export ECEC_CONTAINER=$(readlink -f ecec.sif)
> cd ../runtime

# assume container-experiment.yml is set up for the experiment
> ecec -i <initial data directory> \
      -r <run directory> container-experiment.yml
```

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The script file `container-experiment.yml` in the last command of the recipe refers to the user defined setup of the model experiment, which is specified in just the same way as for the native (non-containerised) version of EC-Earth4. An example is provided with the source code.

Testing

The main goal of the deliverable is to design, develop and deploy an EC-Earth4 container prototype for a simple model experiment workflow. The final targets for the containerised model are pre-exascale EuroHPC systems, which represent similar, but not identical architectures. However, access to these systems is limited for development activities and the work has therefore been done on a national (Tier-1) supercomputer. Here is an overview of relevant architecture details for the development system and current EuroHPC pre-exascale machines:

	Dev/test system	LUMI-C [31]	Leonardo [32]	MareNostrum5 [33]
CPU architecture	AMD Epyc	AMD Epyc	Intel Sapphire Rapids	Intel Sapphire Rapids
Cores per node	32	128	56	112
Interconnect	Intel OmniPath	Slingshot	InfiniBand	InfiniBand
OpenMPI support for interconnect	OFI/libfabric multi-rails support via PSM2	OFI/libfabric	UCX	UCX
Batch system	SLURM	SLURM	SLURM	SLURM
Apptainer support	yes	yes	yes	most likely yes, but not documented

The foundation of performance portability between these platforms lies in the OpenMPI support for different interconnect hardware, in particular the runtime configuration by means of the Modular Component Architecture (MCA). Although it is a complex task to optimise performance by adapting the runtime configuration for performance on the actual target machine, it is also an optional and gradual step that may or may not be necessary depending on the use case.

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The containerised EC-Earth4 version has been tested on the development system by running ten year experiments in the coupled atmosphere-ocean-sea-ice (GCM) configuration. The experiments have been using the standard queues on the system and were set up as ten one-year legs with automatic restarts, thus testing batch job submission from within the container. Two different resolution configurations have been tested, varying the atmosphere resolution between EC-Earth4 standard (TL255L91) and low-resolution (TL159L91). Although not entirely decisive for the outcome of the deliverable, the computational performance of the experiments is documented here:

	containerised	native
TL159L91 - eORCA1L75	ca. 26 SYPD	ca. 42 SYPD
TL255L91 - eORCA1L75	ca. 11 SYPD	ca. 35 SYPD

It becomes clear that without further optimisation, the container version is considerably slower than the native, non-containerised model, which is to be expected. However, since none of the EuroHPC pre-exascale supercomputer systems has the exact same interconnect as the development system - and because it is not quite within the scope of this deliverable - no extensive optimisation and adaptation of the MCA parameters has been done. Despite the inferior computational performance of the unoptimised container, it still allows to run the model on the machine for realistic experiments without any porting effort (e.g. without installing any Python environments nor loading any software modules for compilers, libraries, etc.).

Current issues and further development

- Apptainer availability:
 - Test system provides Apptainer only on compute nodes, which needs special treatment (interactive job needed for container build and run).
 - Check Apptainer installations on EuroHPC systems and adapt recipes if needed.
- Performance optimisation
 - Test OpenMPI/MCA parameter effects on computational performance on a specific system.
 - Develop guidelines and/or recipes for MCA parameter optimisation for common interconnect hardware and EuroHPC systems.

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6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

The deliverable has been delayed by three months due to delays in the release schedule of EC-Earth 4.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the EuroHPC strategy

n/a

8. Sustainability

The software developed for the containerisation of EC-Earth4 (container definition files, runscripts, wrapper scripts, container experiment examples), are included in the version control system and repository used for the main development by the EC-Earth consortium. Compatibility with the main development line of the model is ensured by checking for merge conflicts. The documentation in this deliverable and the actual code will be the basis for the WP4 services on containerisation and also for the training material for WP5, which facilitates a clear uptake path for the developments.

9. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU).
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	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

The containerised version of EC-Earth4 is immediately available to the EC-Earth community through the Gitlab platform. By publishing the deliverable document, other Earth system model developers can make use of the approach and most implementation details for their own developments. The containerised EC-Earth4 version will be the basis for the WP4 service on containerisation, which will facilitate non-developer users that may want to apply the container version on their platform (subject to service call procedures). Moreover, the containerisation approach will be taken up by WP5, producing training material and actual tutorials for the containerisation, addressing an even wider audience.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
SMHI Workshop on containerisation basics	Not specific to EC-Earth, basics of containerisation	November 11, 2023	Software developers	n/a	ca. 25
Publication of code on Gitlab	Development branch for containerisation	continuous, since May 2024	EC-Earth developers	n/a	ca. 40

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

n/a

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

n/a